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Research Article

**EFFECTS OF HELP EXTENDING AFFECTIVE AND
COGNITIVE DOMAINS TO UNDERSTAND THE FEELINGS OF
BELIEVES WHICH CAUSE POVERTY**¹Dr Miran Bakhsh, ²Dr. Hassan Mehmood Raja, ³Dr. Zara Riaz¹MO THQ Hospital Burewala, ²UHS, Lahore, ³Rawalpindi Medical University.**Article Received:** July 2019**Accepted:** August 2019**Published:** September 2019**Abstract:**

This research assessed the consistency of cognitive and affective domains with respect to moderate relationship strength between help extending motives and attitudes for poor on a total of 198 participants in order to measure their feelings for the poor (affective domain) and believes about the poverty causing elements (cognitive domain). Cognitive-affective consistency moderates the degree of the attitudes, which help in the prediction of the allocation of welfare, volunteering to assist and help the poor. These attitudes also significantly predict the participant's decisions who possesses feelings for the poor and believes in the elements causing poverty.

Keywords: Attitudes, Poverty, Believe, Cognitive, Affective, Consistency, Attribution and Poverty.

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INTRODUCTION:

USA poverty rate is estimated about 15.1% as reported in the Census of 2011 [1]. This poverty rate is at an increase of 3% due to economic recession. Even in the strong economic era, 10% were still living below poverty line [2]. Concerns have been posed by the social scientists in order to evaluate attitudes towards poor on the assumptions with consequential poverty discourse framing, public policy impact such as welfare, willingness of the assistance extending by the societal groups and feelings towards poor. Social scientists also believe that there is a variation in the behavior and attitude [3]. We need to identify the attitude characteristics which assist to identify strong and impactful attitudes from weaker and less influential attitudes [4]. Particular importance is given to the assessment of the strength of the attitudes as attitudes are presumably important to take the right decisions. A greater attention is to be given to the strength associated characteristics about attitudes and feelings towards the poor.

Our research examines the attitudes with respect to two different results respectively allocation of resources and volunteering to assist the poor in general public welfare. We also separately measured feelings for the poor (affective domain) and believes about the poverty causing elements (cognitive domain). Cognitive-affective consistency moderates the degree of the attitudes which help in the prediction of the allocation of welfare, volunteering to assist and help the poor.

ATTITUDES, FEELINGS AND BELIEFS:

Attitude is a tendency or predisposition which evaluates some degree of disfavor or favor towards someone [5]. Moreover, this evaluative tendency is a mental residue reflecting behavioral, cognitive and affective reactions to the attitude recipient [6]. Cognitive reactions compose in the presence of positive and negative feelings for the poor with compromised affective reactions. These positively or negatively formed beliefs also affect the strong implications of causes of poverty [7]. For instance, if an individual considers poor's as lazy is totally dispositional and individualistic; whereas, poor are working hard is situational and structural. Blames are also put on the poor economy. Majority of the scholars have focused attributions while studying the attitude towards the poor in their research works [8 – 10]. Few authors have proposed various determinants of poverty which include alcohol abuse, drug, lower level of intelligence, laziness as individualistic causes; whereas, few are of the opinion that these are structural

in nature which include attending bad schools, low wages and employment discrimination [11 – 13].

In addition, culture of traditional nuclear family breakage also attributes in the factor of poverty. This category is less distinct in nature which is a blend of structural and individualistic causes of poverty. It also has factors which can be controlled [14]. Working less is also a contributor in the overall proportions of poverty; it is unfortunate that strength of the attitudes also differ within the effect of cognition and behavior is predicted differently in terms of feelings and beliefs [15].

Cozzarelli et al. evaluated feelings among college students and reported poor presented positive attitude [16]. However, strongly endorsed attributes about poor were uneducated, socially irresponsible and lazy including alcohol and drug abuse [17]. It is important to note that there are significant association between attributions and feelings towards poor with weaker association of structural and individualistic attributes. Therefore, outcomes suggest about the beliefs and feelings about poor have inconsistency to some extent within these beliefs and feelings.

Tetlock and Skitka (1992) found that participants denied to fund the poor as they considered them responsible for their poverty due to loss of job and drug abuse. Other reasons of poverty also included genetic learning disability which resulted in uncontrollable lack of income or economy slump as an external factor causing poverty [18, 19]. Few others also conducted studies on the similar lines by asking participants to judge the recommendation of financial assistance for unemployed recipients. More funds were released by the participants to loss of jobs and unemployed individuals fighting to meet the both ends meet than of those who had poor working habits [20].

AFFECTIVE-COGNITIVE CONSISTENCY:

Attitudes are mental residues for prior behavioral, cognitive and affective reactions which can logically be further theorized to differentiate reactions and relations. Attitude strength is marked by the consistency of a reaction. Behavior is predicted through impact-fullness and durability of the attitude. In the past several decades there has been a lot of work in the field of attitudes but it is unfortunate that it does not significantly predict the terminal behavior [21]. We have identified strength associated characteristics of the attitudes which include knowledge, accessibility, structural consistency and importance [22]. The objective of this research was to evaluate the role of these strengths in order to assess the attitude

towards poor. Rosenberg proposed that we can measure the degree of evaluative consistency for the assessment of attitudes consistency between beliefs and feelings [22]. Quantitatively, ACC did not depend on the overall position of the attitude including likeness or dis-likeness. Higher ACC correspond to the relation of an attitude object having a consistent evaluative property with reports of positive feelings for the poor while believing that have been struck by the circumstances. A weak relationship between beliefs and feelings refers to lower ACC [23]. This research study was designed to evaluate the potential moderating role of ACC in the decisions and attitudes towards poor relationship which ultimately assist the poor. Budget allocation decision in the government sector programs refer to welfare-oriented approaches to counter poverty through volunteer pledge and food bank. Our hypothesis about the decisions to assist poor significantly predict better feelings towards poor with related beliefs about the poverty and its causes that corresponds to higher ACC than inconsistent beliefs and feelings which corresponds to lower ACC.

METHOD & PARTICIPANTS:

Participants were in the mean age of (19.12 ± 2.06) years. The class distribution was made through scale class system including lower, middle and upper-class system. Most of the participants belonged to middle or just higher-class families (4.30 ± 1.00). Participants were more conservative than liberal (4.07 ± 1.08). There was no significant role of the economic status, political ideology, ethnicity and age in the reported

analysis. We collected data in the scheduled one-hour sessions in the classroom environment. We also described research differences among people about opinions, beliefs and feelings with respect to other groups regarding interactions and policies. Participants were included in the research after an informed consent. They also filled up a questionnaire containing balanced questions about allocations measures, cognition, affects and attitudes. Volunteer inclusion was also asked for the food bank by the participants after the filling up of questionnaire. Participants were debriefed in detail about the purpose of volunteering themselves which was further forwarded to food bank. Participants were also encouraged to volunteer themselves by giving their contact information.

RESULTS:

The outcomes have been reported with the help of detailed descriptive statistics and bivariate correlations. Overall feelings and attitudes toward the poor were moderate and positive; whereas, strong endorsements were reported for individualistic rather structural attributions. We also significantly associated feelings and attitudes with volunteer decision and welfare allocations. We did not correlate feelings and attitudes with volunteer measures taken. ACC was associated with decision to volunteer and welfare allocations but not with the pledged hours of the volunteer. Detailed outcomes have also been presented in the given tabular data:

Table – I: Descriptive Statistics & Bivariate Associations

Variables	Mean	SD	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Attitudes	4.36	1.13	0.72	0.3	0.15	0.11	0.18	0.15	0.15
Feelings	3.63	0.64	-	0.3	0.24	0.09	0.29	0.19	0.18
Individualistic Features	3.24	0.67	-	-	-15	-0.02	0.31	-0.11	-0.08
Structural Features	2.43	0.65	-	-	-	-0.05	0.33	0.05	0.13
ACC	0.92	0.67	-	-	-	-	0.19	-0.22	-0.12
Welfare Allocation	11.88	6.97	-	-	-	-	-	0.18	0.13
Volunteer Intention	0.29	0.46	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.78
Hours Pledged	2.18	4.84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table – II: Hierarchical Multiple Regression Predicting Welfare Allocation

Variable		b	SE	β	t	R ²	ΔR^2
Model - I	Attitude	1.24	0.43	0.2	2.88	0.07	0.02
	ACC	-2.11	0.73	-0.2	-2.88		
Model - II	Attitude	1.37	0.43	0.22	3.18	0.09	
	ACC	-1.98	0.73	-0.19	-2.17		
	Attitude x ACC	-1.2	0.58	-0.15	-2.08		

Table – III: Hierarchical Logistic Regression Predicting Volunteer Intentions

Variable		b	SE	Wald	OR	X ²	ΔX^2
Model - I	Attitude	0.37	0.15	6.07	1.44	16.42	5.64
	ACC	-0.92	0.28	10.62	0.4		
Model - II	Attitude	0.34	0.16	4.63	1.41	22.06	
	ACC	-0.81	0.28	8.31	0.45		
	Attitude x ACC	-0.56	0.25	5.11	0.57		

Table – IV: Hierarchical Multiple Regression Volunteer Hours Pledged

Variable		b	SE	β	t	R ²	ΔR^2
Model - I	Attitude	0.7	0.31	0.17	2.29	0.04	0.02
	ACC	-0.95	0.52	-0.13	-1.82		
Model - II	Attitude	0.78	0.31	0.18	2.53	0.06	
	ACC	-0.85	0.52	-0.12	-1.64		
	Attitude x ACC	-0.77	0.41	-0.14	-1.87		

Table – V: Hierarchical Multiple Regression Predicting Hours Pledged for Long Transformation

Variable		b	SE	β	t	R ²	ΔR^2
Model - I	Attitude	0.07	0.03	0.19	2.6	0.08	0.04
	ACC	-0.14	0.04	-0.22	-3.13		
Model - II	Attitude	0.08	0.03	0.21	2.97	0.11	
	ACC	-0.13	0.04	-0.2	-2.9		
	Attitude x ACC	-0.09	0.03	-0.19	-2.69		

DISCUSSION:

Attitudes significantly predict volunteer intentions and welfare allocations with consistent beliefs and feelings. This is not same in the inconsistent state of both. Few positive aspects of the research include separate evaluation of beliefs and feelings which is also accepted in the social psychological attitude conceptions and also permits an independent assessment of ACC in the attitude construct [24, 25]. This research also reviewed literature about previously studies on the topic of poverty and budget allocation as well [26 – 29]. This research is unique in nature. It is to be acknowledged that measures of beliefs and feelings are not completely empirical and distinct measure of cognition and affect. On reporting beliefs and feelings, responding process may initiate both cognition and affective with limited extent [30]. Beliefs and feelings also have a synergetic association with attitude [31]. Existing measures were opted to measure beliefs and feelings towards poor which were reliable in nature and have already been tested by various authors [32]. More information can be gathered through novel measures in the future research. Open and closed ended measures also allow the respondents to genuinely hold beliefs and feelings across the attitude's objects [33]. Few research limitations include documentation of time spent on volunteer help, information about the volunteer, willingness, interested tasks and public welfare decisions. Future behavior is best predicted through behavioral intentions [34]. Various authors have also found different predicting attitudes among various age groups ranging from young to old such as 65 to 75 years in terms of self-reported volunteering to help the community [35].

Welfare allocation was highly dependent on the poverty attributions; however, it did not predict hours spent on volunteer jobs and intentions of the individuals. These outcomes also suggest about the large-scale social policies for the judgement of the assisting attitude to the deservingness perceptions than local community assisting decisions and personal assistance initiatives [36]. In the presence of these difference, attitudes predicted both volunteer

measures and welfare allocations. Similarly, ACC also predicted volunteer measures and welfare allocations. Hypothesis says that ACC significantly moderates those attitudes which predict volunteer intentions and welfare allocations with consistent beliefs and feelings that play a vital part in the outcomes of help-giving. There are two reasons to support the outcomes of this research; firstly, it has additional evidence about the moderating ACC role in attitudes and secondly it continued the research work on behavioral outcomes and strength-related features of attitude which alleviate poverty. Huge amount of literature is available on the strength associated characteristics of attitudes; whereas, few authors have also assessed structural consistency [37 – 38].

CONCLUSION:

Attitudes are essentially crucial which can measure the treatment with the poor. Attitudes, if understood, can be altered and positive variations can be brought for favorable anti-poverty campaigns and drives. It will help to formulate effective poverty countering policies for reliable changes. Just reporting about the positive attitude may not suffice as a good predictor. ACC moderating role in the light of presented outcomes and indicators can best predict the actual behavior which will support legislation related to anti-poverty. It will also increase the positive beliefs and feelings about towards poor. Such influences are also challenging with different degrees as middle class endorses ideological beliefs which mostly emphasize an individualistic approach and also poses negative effects on the economic recession which ripens the attitudes changes.

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